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ATTITUDES OF PUBLIC JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL TEACHERS TOWARD RESEARCH IN THE NEW NORMAL: BASIS FOR AN ORIENTATION PROGRAM

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Abstract

The basic research attempted to determine the attitudes of teachers toward research of faculty members of Burgos National High School, Main Campus and Sorrento Extension during the school year 2021- 2022. The research adopted the descriptive method and utilized the standardized and validated questionnaire from Attitudes Toward Research Scale of Papanastasiou (2014). The population of the study consisted of 107 teachers from the two campuses of the school. Total population sampling was considered because of the relatively small size population. Weighted mean and t- test were used to determine the attitudes of teachers toward research and measure the significant difference between the two groups of respondents on the attitudes toward research, respectively. The results of the research showed the following findings: (1) The teacher respondents' attitudes toward research in terms of a) Research Usefulness-Strongly Agree b) Anxiety-Agree c) Positive Research Predispositions-Agree. (2) The results further showed that that there was no significant difference in the assessment of the two groups of respondents on the attitudes of teachers toward research. (3) An orientation program on basic and action research writing was formulated out of the results of the study. The research was focused only on the attitudes of teachers toward research in terms of research usefulness, anxiety, and positive research predispositions. The result of the research was a big leap in nurturing the teachers to the world of research, thus rooting out the source of some problems in the classroom and school setting.

Keywords: attitudes toward research, anxiety, positive research disposition, research usefulness

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